

A Case for DoD Application of Public Cloud Computing Services

Kris E Barcomb
Jeffrey W Humphries
Robert F Mills

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Air Force Institute of Technology
Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, USA

Abstract— Cloud computing offers tremendous opportunities for private industry, governments, and even individuals to access massive amounts of compute resources on-demand at very low cost. Recent advancements in bandwidth availability, virtualization, security services and general public awareness have contributed to this information technology (IT) business model. Cloud computing provides on-demand scalability, reduces costs, decreases barriers to entry, and enables organizations to refocus on core competencies. Despite the benefits, security concerns are still the dominant barriers to cloud service adoption. This article explores public cloud computing from a Department of Defense (DoD) perspective. The objective is to improve the general understanding, analyze security issues, and present recommendations to the DoD to help foster public cloud computing adoption.

Keywords - Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Infrastructure as a Service, Information Technology, Data Centers

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing offers tremendous opportunities for private industry, governments, and even individuals, to access massive amounts of compute resources on-demand at very low cost. The business model for cloud computing is similar to that of a public utility [1]. Central providers assume responsibility for the substantial capital investment, and the operations and maintenance functions for large IT infrastructures. Consumers pay for access to those resources according to the amount they use. The resources are provided, usually over the public Internet, to consumers on-demand. Providers deliver low-cost solutions by distributing their own costs across the large volume of consumers who benefit from their services.

This article is primarily concerned with public cloud computing services for two reasons. First, public providers benefit by leveraging the tremendous economies of scale of the commercial market place, which drives down consumer costs. Second, competition spurs innovation and continuous improvement. Government agencies deploying private cloud solutions are unlikely to achieve comparable costs or maintain pace with advances in commercial IT. As Waxer observes, private infrastructures can rarely match the service levels offered by public cloud providers [2].

This article explores the benefits of cloud computing and examines risk management when leveraging external IT

providers from the perspective of Federal law, standards and DoD doctrine. It concludes with five recommendations to help foster DoD adoption of public cloud computing services.

II. CLOUD COMPUTING DEFINITION

The best broad definition comes from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), which describes cloud computing as “a model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g. networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction. This cloud model promotes availability and is composed of five essential characteristics, three service models and four deployment models” [3].

A. Cloud Computing Essential Characteristics

The five essential characteristics describe the nature of a true cloud computing implementation and help scope the requirements for implementing a cloud service offering. They also provide a framework of basic criteria for evaluating the quality of one implementation over another.

On-Demand Self-Service describes how providers dynamically allocate resources to consumers upon request. The consumers drive the requests, and there is generally little-to-no human interaction required after the service level agreement (SLA) between the consumer and the provider is established. *Broad Network Access* means that sufficient network availability and bandwidth are present. *Resource Pooling* describes how providers leverage the economies of scale generated by spreading demand from multiple consumers across the provider’s resource pool using technologies like virtualization, dynamic provisioning, and load balancing. *Rapid Elasticity* describes how resources can quickly be added to, or removed from, the consumer’s pool of allocated resources, so they can operate with the exact amount required to perform a given task. Finally, *Measured Service* enables providers to quantify the costs of allocated resources per unit time and subsequently charge a consumer for only what is used.

B. Cloud Computing Service Models

The cloud computing service models describe the level of functionality offered by the provider. At higher levels, the consumer receives more functionality and knows less about the

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implementation details. The higher layers can also be built upon services received from lower levels. At lower levels, the consumer receives more granularity and higher levels of control. They are also increasingly responsible for the implementation details. The lowest levels can provide services that look and feel very much like locally hosted hardware.

1) *Software as a Service (SaaS)*: At this highest layer, consumers gain access to fully functional applications without having to install or locally manage application software. The SaaS provider is responsible for the implementation details as well as the hardware resources. The provider also retains responsibility for maintenance and configuration management of the application. The consumer generally has little to no knowledge of how, or even where, the operations run. This model's strength is that consumers can often operate these services from client platforms ranging from thick clients down to web-enabled mobile devices. Also, the application state can often be seamlessly maintained from one device to another.

2) *Platform as a Service (PaaS)*: PaaS providers offer a balance of functionality and control that falls in-between SaaS and IaaS. PaaS offerings are analogous to an application programming interface where the complexities and redundancy associated with generating low-level code is abstracted away from the user. Consumers use PaaS to generate custom applications using software development languages and tools offered by the provider. The provider then hosts the resulting application on its own hardware which is provisioned according to client demand.

3) *Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)*: This lowest level of service provides consumers with the most control over their environment. In its purest form, IaaS provisions hardware resources directly and leaves most of the details of what to put on that hardware, including the operating system (OS), in the hands of the user. In practice, IaaS is often implemented using virtualization technologies serving to abstract the underlying hardware from the applications. The user generally does not know the specific configuration of the underlying hardware.

Virtualization within an IaaS offering has a number of other key features that are advantageous to both consumers and providers. Virtualized implementations enable the provider to manage the underlying hardware more efficiently than if applications were implemented through "bare-metal" installations. This helps reduce the overall cost to both the consumer and provider. Virtualization also serves to isolate one consumer from another even when multiple consumer applications reside on the same physical resources. Isolation reduces the risk of errors in one application from having adverse affects on other user's applications. When properly configured, it also provides a security barrier between consumers by encapsulating information within a set of logically separated resources ensuring that different users cannot access one another's applications or data [4]. Virtualization can also streamline configuration management and enable more efficient scalability by allowing consumers to manage the security configuration, patch level, software versioning and implementation details in a single virtual machine instance. The provider can then dynamically replicate that instance across as many resources as necessary.

C. Cloud Computing Deployment Models

There are four deployment models for cloud computing: *Public, Private, Hybrid and Community*. A public cloud is implemented by a cloud service provider who makes those services available to external entities. The provider is responsible for all of the capital and operating expense of the underlying infrastructure. It spreads that cost across all of its consumers either through a direct fee or through revenue generated from advertisements. A private cloud operates entirely within an organization and provides services only to its own members. The organization can tailor the services it provides to meet its specific needs, but it must bear all of the costs associated with acquiring and managing the associated IT resources. An organization implements a hybrid cloud by putting some of its functionality within its own private cloud and outsources the rest to a public cloud provider. Community clouds distribute the cost and management burden of a cloud architecture across different organizations with similar objectives or interests.

III. BENEFITS OF PUBLIC CLOUD COMPUTING

Public cloud computing can provide many advantages to DoD managers willing to incorporate its services into their IT architectures. This article focuses on five aspects of public cloud computing that are especially relevant to the DoD:

1) *Continuous Refresh*: DoD acquisition managers are under constant pressure to maintain currency across their enterprises and meet ever changing requirements over an increasingly complex infrastructure. It is extremely difficult to achieve such lofty goals under layers of bureaucracy and a six-year Planning, Programming, Budgeting, and Execution (PPBE) cycle. Information technologies are driven by the dynamic market trends and can rarely, if ever, be predicted years in advance through a centralized requirements process.

Market forces and competition between cloud service providers benefit the DoD as those pressures drive them to maintain the typical 12-24 month commercial IT refresh cycles. This is also one of the key advantages of a virtualized solution. Since virtualization abstracts the hardware from applications, it allows applications to migrate more easily between hardware platforms and facilitates system upgrades.

2) *Rapid Elasticity*: One of NIST's essential elements is also one of cloud computing's predominant benefits. It goes hand-in-hand with overcoming the dynamic nature of IT requirements. Elasticity describes how cloud computing resources grow or shrink to match demand. This capability translates into more relaxed constraints on early estimates of resource requirements because the available resource pool can adapt to meet changing needs.

Animoto's use of Amazon's Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) is an example of the power of rapid elasticity. Animoto creates video montages automatically from user provided photos and music. In 2008, when they launched their service as a Facebook application, the demand for their service spiked forcing them to grow from 50 processing servers to over 3,500 in just 3 days. This was only possible because they had built

their service using Amazon's EC2, which enabled them to meet the unpredictable demand for their product [5].

3) *Lower Cost*: The historically stovepiped nature of DoD acquisition programs have led to infrastructure redundancy and underutilization. A 2010 memorandum from Vivek Kundra, the Federal Chief Information Officer (CIO), highlighted the DoD as having 772 individual data centers; the largest number as compared to all other federal agencies [6]. In a keynote speech to the Brookings Institution in April 2007, he also stated that utilization rates for government data centers are typically only around seven percent. Data centers go underutilized because they were designed to handle a given application's peak load, which only occurs over a limited period of time. For the majority of the time, these assets sit idle. The separated nature of the DoD compute infrastructure adds to the problem by prohibiting one system from sharing its processing or storage load with other systems.

Typically, a single user or application has a cyclical demand for resources that spikes at certain times, but goes unused at others. Therefore, public providers host many different customers in their infrastructures simultaneously. This characteristic of cloud computing is known as "multi-tenancy". Public cloud service providers dynamically distribute application loads from multiple users across multiple systems. They capitalize on the statistical nature of the loads generated by several consumers over time. As one user's demand drops, the provider reclaims resources from that user and reprovisions them to another user whose demand is rising. This is how public cloud computing providers maintain high utilization rates across their infrastructures. The utilization rates have a direct relationship to overall costs.

4) *Improved mission focus*: One useful way of framing the types of organizations on the Internet is to consider Application Service Providers (ASPs) and Internet Service Providers (ISPs). The two functions are separable, but highly dependent on each other for providing a complete product to consumers. In its most basic form, the ISP provides consumers with connectivity to the Internet. The ASP creates applications that ride on top of that infrastructure and add value to it. For example, Comcast, Verizon, AT&T and Time Warner are all examples of ISPs. Facebook, Bing, eBay, and Wikipedia are examples of ASPs. The separability of these two functions allows each organization to focus on its core competencies without having to be experts in all aspects of the complicated, end-to-end solution required to deliver applications to users over the web.

By following the ASP/ISP model, the DoD can more effectively focus on its mission. Decoupling the mission applications and information from the underlying IT infrastructure will allow the DoD to provide better mission services. Public cloud computing providers can become the ISP for many DoD applications. The DoD can leverage the provider's expertise and ultimately produce more agile and lower-cost solutions.

5) *Lower Barriers to Entry*: This last benefit gets to the heart of the DoD industry base. Mergers and acquisitions, budget cuts and short-sighted planning have led to a competition pool dominated by a handful of massive prime

contractors. This not only dilutes the economic market forces that help lower acquisition costs, but also stifles innovation.

Application processing, storage and connectivity requirements keep most small business and non-traditional defense contractors out of the available pool of bidders. Often, these companies have ideas and talent that could provide the DoD with tremendous benefit, but they cannot overcome contractual barriers such as access to government furnished equipment or meeting the myriad security requirements for connectivity. Harauz et al. describes the benefits of cloud computing to small businesses as a "major selling point" [7].

IV. ASSESSING SECURITY FROM A RISK MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE

International Data Corporation (IDC) conducted a survey in 2009 asking IT executives and CIOs to "rate the challenges/issues of the cloud/on-demand model." Not surprisingly, security topped the list at 87.5% of respondents rating it as a concern [8]. The answer would almost assuredly be the same or even higher if the same poll was conducted within the DoD. Unfortunately, the current business model for managing DoD IT security cannot be sustained in a declining budget environment with users demanding better services.

Wyld captures the essence of much of the problem for government IT managers by correlating the perception that *having control* is the same as *being secure*. He backs up this premise with quotes from Arun Gupta, a partner at Columbia Capital, and another from Linda Cureton, CIO of NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center. Gupta states that to succeed "You have to have the confidence to say, 'I don't need to control everything'". Cureton said that it is imperative when considering cloud computing not to "confuse control and ownership with security and viability" [9]. Golden amplifies these statements by observing that those who characterize cloud computing as too risky often have an overly optimistic view of their current risk management practices. He goes on to say, "this attitude reflects a common human condition: underestimating the risks associated with current conditions while overestimating the risks of something new" [10].

Successful adoption of public cloud computing requires security to be evaluated from a risk management perspective rather than one of risk avoidance. In addition, IT managers must resist the urge to equate their level of control with their level of security. Understanding the regulations governing IT is a critical component of making that risk determination.

A. Federal Information Security Management Act of 2002

FISMA was enacted under Title III of the E-Government Act of 2002 (Public Law 107-347). It requires each federal agency to "develop, document, and implement an agency-wide program to provide information security for the information and information systems that support the operations and assets of the agency, including those provided or managed by another agency, contractor, or other source." Under FISMA, NIST was tasked with the responsibility for developing the standards and guidelines for categorizing all information and information systems, recommending the types of information and information systems to be included in each category, and

developing the minimum information security requirements for information and information systems in each category. From this tasking NIST generated Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS) Publication 199 and 200, and Special Publication (SP) 800-53.

FISMA defines three security objectives that serve as the basis for NIST's analysis: *Confidentiality*, *Integrity*, and *Availability*. *Confidentiality* means "preserving authorized restrictions on information access and disclosure, including means for protecting personal privacy and proprietary information." *Integrity* means "guarding against improper information modification or destruction, and includes ensuring information non-repudiation and authenticity." Finally, *Availability* means "ensuring timely and reliable access to and use of information" [11].

B. FIPS 199: Standards for Security Categorization of Federal Information and Information Systems

FIPS 199 addresses NIST's responsibility to develop standards for categorizing information and information systems. This document first describes the nature of the impact associated with the loss of one of the three security objectives defined by FISMA:

- A loss of *confidentiality* is the unauthorized disclosure of information.
- A loss of *integrity* is the unauthorized modification or destruction of information.
- A loss of *availability* is the disruption of access to or use of information or an information system.

With this framework in mind, NIST presents a generalized formula for agencies to express the Security Category (SC) of their information and information systems. Establishing an appropriate SC requires IT managers to determine the potential impact, as Low ("limited adverse effect"), Medium ("serious adverse effect") or High ("severe or catastrophic adverse effect"), for each security objective associated with a particular information type. The overall SC is based on the "high water mark concept" meaning that an information system's SC will be no less than the highest impact category over all security objectives. Security categorization of federal information and information systems starts the risk management process [12].

C. FIPS 200: Minimum Security Requirements for Federal Information and Information Systems

FIPS 200 is the second of the mandatory security standards required by FISMA. It specifies the minimum security requirements covering seventeen security related areas for protecting confidentiality, integrity and availability of federal information systems and the information processed, stored, and transmitted by those systems. The security-related areas are: *access control; awareness & training; audit & accountability; certification, accreditation, & security assessments; configuration management; contingency planning; identification & authentication; incident response; maintenance; media protection; physical & environmental protection; planning; personnel security; risk assessment; systems & services acquisition; system & communications protection; and system & information integrity* [11].

D. Special Publication 800-53

After completing the security categorization process described in FIPS 199, organizations select an appropriate set of security controls for their information systems that satisfy the minimum security requirements set forth in FIPS 200. NIST SP 800-53 lays out security controls tailored for both the security area and for the impact level determined during the security categorization process [13]. Ultimately, it is the responsibility of the organization to select security controls appropriate to their specific systems.

SP 800-53 recognizes the challenge and importance associated with selecting the most cost-effective controls, which can drive managers to leverage externally provided services. Particular challenges outlined include defining the types of external services provided; describing how the external services are protected; and obtaining necessary assurances that the risk to the organization's operations and assets, and to individuals, is at an acceptable level.

The primary consideration presented for overcoming these challenges is trust. Trust provides confidence that the risk to the organization's operations, assets and individuals is at an acceptable level. Federal agencies can manage the level of trust by exerting a certain amount of direct control over the external provider with contracts or SLAs. Trust can also develop from external providers convincing Federal agencies they have credible security controls in place. This may be accomplished through third party audits or authoritative certifications of a provider's security control mechanisms.

E. DoD Information Assurance

DoD Directive 8500.01E "Information Assurance (IA)" and DoD Instruction 8500.2 "Information Assurance (IA) Implementation" are the most applicable documents for analyzing DoD specific IT requirements impacting public cloud computing adoption. Analogous to FISMA and NIST documentation, 8500.01E lays out an overarching framework and 8500.2 provides specific controls required to secure DoD information systems.

8500.01E restates that DoD information systems must to be categorized according to their required levels of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability. Appropriate levels for Integrity and Availability are combined into one of three *Mission Assurance Categories (MACs)*. MAC I systems require the highest Integrity and Availability and MAC III is reserved for systems that do not materially affect support to on-going operations [14].

8500.2 presents the MAC and confidentiality levels in nine possible combinations and establishes the IA controls required for each possibility. The specific IA controls can be used as a basis for the SLA and contract between the program manager (PM) and the cloud service provider. Unfortunately, 8500.2 takes a negative view of external services by highlighting them as one of the primary factors that contribute to vulnerabilities without balancing that view with the security strengths that external services often provide [15].

F. Bridging the Gap

The framework established by FISMA, NIST and the DoD, provide a comprehensive risk management structure for securing information systems. It helps establish a basis for evaluating the security posture of public cloud computing providers with respect to agency requirements. As highlighted in SP 800-53 and the DoD documentation, trust is a primary consideration and it will continue to develop over time. Fortunately, external providers are making strides to help establish that trust. For example, in November 2009, Amazon Web Services (AWS) successfully completed a Statement on Auditing Standards 70 Type II audit and in November 2010, they were awarded an International Organization for Standardization 20001 certification. In addition, a Department of Education application, with a security category of LOW under FISMA regulation, received the necessary Authority to Operate using AWS [16]. Google Apps for Government achieved similar certifications and even offers segregated systems for US government only use [17].

The Federal government is also taking proactive steps to strengthen the trust between external providers and federal agencies. The Federal CIO's office recently launched the Federal Risk and Authorization Management Program (FedRAMP). The program was established to "provide a standard approach to assessing and authorizing cloud computing services and products. FedRAMP allows joint authorizations and continuous security monitoring services for Government and Commercial cloud computing systems intended for multi-agency use." It also aims to provide a risk model enabling the government to "approve once, and use often" [18]. This program should help streamline the approval process for public cloud computing services and enable IT managers to capitalize on their benefits.

DoD managers should also understand that commercial cloud service providers are highly incentivized to take a proactive stance toward security. In June 2010, IDC forecasted that worldwide revenue from public IT cloud services would reach \$55.5 billion in 2014 [19]. Providers recognize that despite some technical challenges, there are not significant barriers preventing consumers from switching from one provider to another. A sufficient security breach could result in a tremendous loss of revenue as consumers make that change. These financial realities make security a top priority.

Much work has been done to help address the minimum security requirements outlined in FIPS 200 and 8500.2. Most cloud computing providers have built their business models around common security best practices. Physical security, distributed data replication, personnel training and monitoring, audit logging, patch configuration management, data encryption, secure authentication, network firewall management and intrusion detection are well established and are often reviewed by independent auditors [17] [20] [21]. Researchers are also constantly investigating ways to make the cloud more palatable for both the government and private industry. Examples include *Fabric*, a platform for securing distributed workloads [22]; *Terra*, a trusted computing platform for virtual machines [23]; the *Trusted Cloud Computing Platform* for guaranteeing confidential execution

of guest virtual machines in IaaS environments [24]; and cloud security solutions based on virtual-machine introspection [25].

With these facts in mind, DoD managers must resist the urge to fall back on the status quo. In addition, they must not draw incorrect conclusions that regulatory compliance necessarily excludes public cloud computing as some have in the past [26].

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The focus will now turn toward a series of five recommendations to help the DoD integrate public cloud computing into its IT enterprise.

1) *Education*: DoD IT managers must be educated on the benefits and challenges of using public cloud computing. Many managers are unaware that these services even exist. Once a general awareness is established, then those managers will be able to assess the pros and cons of the technologies and business models associated with public cloud computing in a more thorough manner.

The DoD must also focus its terminology for describing cloud computing. The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing should be used throughout the DoD. Employing a consistent vocabulary will help managers generate better requirements and help the DoD communicate with public service providers through more precise SLAs and contracts. Kandukuri *et al.* provide an excellent discussion of how to appropriately craft SLAs to handle security issues with cloud computing providers [27].

2) *Adopt Risk Management over Risk Avoidance*: Risk management is a critical aspect of all acquisition. It helps PMs evaluate the risk versus reward of one option over another. Unfortunately, DoD PMs are often reluctant to allow external IT services into their option space because of the perception that their level of control is proportional to the security of their system. Hopefully, with a better understanding of cloud computing, a determined Federal CIO behind them, and continuous improvements in the security posture of public cloud providers, PMs will take a closer look at public cloud computing IT architectures.

3) *Investigate the Value Proposition*: Equation 1 presents a formula for evaluating the cost benefit of a public cloud computing solution. On-demand, scalability enables the left-hand side of the equation to be centered on actual usage instead of a more traditional cost estimation method based on procuring a data center sized to meet peak operating load.

The left-hand side represents the cost of a public cloud implementation. The first term is the *Usage* (in time units) multiplied by C_{unit} , the unit cost of the service per unit time. $C_{transition}$ represents the transition costs, such as software recoding, of porting existing applications to the cloud. $C_{connectivity}$ represents the cost of the connectivity between the point of service consumption and the cloud platform. The equation then accounts for the estimated reduction in labor and facilities that would have been spent to implement a traditional private solution by subtracting C_{labor} and $C_{facilities}$. Finally, C_{risk} represents management reserve for handling contingencies.

The right-hand side describes the estimated costs of a traditional acquisition as determined through normal cost estimation techniques. All other factors being equal, managers should choose the public cloud computing solution if the left-hand side is less than the right hand side.

$$Usage * C_{unit} + C_{transition} + C_{connectivity} - C_{labor} - C_{facilities} + C_{risk} < C_{traditional\ acquisition} \quad (1)$$

4) *Pilot Programs*: Pilot programs will help develop a practical understanding of how DoD applications can best leverage public cloud computing. They are also essential for determining appropriate performance metrics. Cost is obviously a big factor, but benefits such as rapid elasticity, improved mission focus and lower barriers to entry are more difficult to quantify. Through practice, the DoD can develop more tangible metrics to quantify those kinds of benefits.

At Gartner's 22nd Annual Application Architecture, Development & Integration Summit in 2009, David Cearley and Gene Phifer presented a keynote speech outlining six candidate application classes likely to provide early successes in the cloud: *Prototyping/Proof of Concept; Development/Test & Projects; Web Application Serving; SaaS, E-Mail, Collaboration; Departmental & Workgroup Apps; and Simple Parallelized Workloads*. The DoD should start by looking for these classes of IT programs within its enterprise. Then, it should sort out those that are categorized as MAC II or III that process publicly releasable information. This should produce a set of low-risk, high-reward pilot candidates.

In addition, public IaaS offerings are likely to be the best starting point for cloud service adoption. IaaS provides the consumer with the most control over the environment and as such, the DoD has more opportunities to customize it to match unique security requirements and application designs.

5) *Establish Cloud Computing in the Acquisition Process*: Hopefully, the DoD will recognize the benefits of leveraging public cloud computing as it implements the first four recommendations. Eventually, the DoD should formally establish cloud computing in its acquisition process similar to the "Cloud First" policy of the Federal CIO [28]. PMs should be required to justify decisions to procure private IT solutions over those of external providers at each of the acquisition milestones described in the DoD 5000 series documents. The DoD CIO should lead this effort. This step will help reinforce the need to consolidate the DoD IT infrastructures, encourage standardization across the enterprise, allow for more agile responses to changing user needs, and promote faster acquisitions timelines.

VI. CONCLUSION

The time is right for DoD program managers to seriously consider incorporating public cloud computing services into their IT architectures. These services offer the potential to lower costs, increase agility, improve mission focus and stimulate innovation. DoD managers must take the necessary steps to develop trust with external providers so that they can successfully leveraged the benefits of public cloud computing.

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